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ABSTRACTS

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Effect of Chemical and Bio fertilizers on the Yield of Soybean production

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Abstract: The utilization of biofertilizers is a key point for sustainable agriculture farming and its use is an eye-catching research area to enhance plant growth and yield. The current study delves into the intricate dynamics of soybean cultivation by examining the combined application of chemical and biofertilizers. Emphasizing the pivotal role of soil testing and the meticulous screening of biofertilizers. The research aims to elucidate the interactions that shape their efficacy in soybean production. A focal point of the investigation involves a comparative analysis between the conventional use of chemical fertilizers and the targeted application of carefully screened biofertilizers. The study goes beyond mere yield assessments delving into the intricate details of nutrient value variations resulting from these distinct fertilization approaches. The overarching goal is to offer insights that can inform sustainable agricultural practices, providing a bridge between traditional fertilization methods and innovative environmentally friendly approaches. The anticipated findings hold promise not only for optimizing soybean yields but also for contributing valuable knowledge to the broader discourse on precision agriculture and the quest for resilient and sustainable food production systems.

Keywords: Bio-fertilizers, Bioengineering, Chemical fertilizers, Soya bean, Agricultural farming

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